

Covid-19 pandemic and socio-economic wellbeing of Nigerians

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ABSTRACT

The study is on covid-19 pandemic and socio-economic wellbeing of Nigerians. It is premised on the fact that, the rapid spread of the virus increased drastically and constituted enormous challenges to socio-economic activities as its containment strategies interfered with individuals' daily lives and led to severe economic loss in employment, basic needs and social disruption in educational system of Nigerians despite the directive of ministry of education to learn from home teaching method. Specifically, the paper aimed to ascertain the impact of covid-19 pandemic on education, employment in Nigeria and the satisfaction of basic needs of Nigerian citizens. Data for the study were derived from secondary sources. Notably, it involved content analysis of information gleaned from journals, textbooks, newspapers, web pages and government documents among others. Securitization theory was used as the theoretical framework of the analysis. The findings show that, the-educational system was disrupted as the directives to learn from home could not be effectively complied with by both teachers and students due to the infrastructural deficit such as poor internet connectivity, non-possession of relevant devices like laptops and smart phones and unstable power supply necessary to operate virtual classes, There was also loss of employment because organizations had to either close or scale back operations, and Nigerians, especially the low-income earners could not meet their basic needs because supply could not meet demand and many could not even afford the skyrocketing prices of the few available commodities. The study recommends among other things that: government provide solar powered educational devices, pre-loaded with off-line academic resources especially to the vulnerable communities and disadvantaged students.

Key words: Covid-19 Pandemic, Education, Employment, Socio-Economic, Wellbeing and Nigerians.

Introduction

Corona virus was first discovered in Wuhan, China, in November 2019 and was declared a global pandemic on 11th March 2020. Following that, Nigeria was with several challenges bordering on the rapid spread of the virus that strained the health system and turned it into social and economic emergency despite its containment measures. The restriction order halted all activities, prevented people from pursuing their legitimate economic activities from which they could make money to fend for their families. That interfered with individuals' daily lives as several families faced significant financial challenge. Beyond that, it led to severe economic loss in employment, basic needs and social disruption in educational system. Obioma, Reuben and Elekwachi (2021) reported that; the pandemic shut down everyday activities in all ramifications of lives and

destroyed humanity on account of the fact that relationship that existed between people in the society was reduced and social, economic and other gatherings were disrupted by the containment measures against the virus.

The introduction of containment measures such as social and physical distancing, states lockdown, movement restrictions led to shut down of borders, schools, offices, churches, markets, social gatherings among others. Also, there were temperature checks, and the use of hand sanitizers, nose masks became routine in public places and in homes, (Nwosu-Igbo 2020; Onuh, 2021). Similarly, people began to wrestle with the containment measures in their social and economic lives as activities were halted. Several people were stopped from engaging in economic activities which led to a gross shortage of cash, foodstuffs and translated to poverty, unemployment and threatened human survival. Again, the swift approval by the federal ministry of education on March 19 2020 for closure of all schools caused a significant disruption in the educational system in Nigeria in such areas as learning modes and access to school related services, (The Education Partnership Centre, 2020). More so, it led to a soaring number of adults, youths and children unable to attend schools. It was on account of the foregoing that, the study examines the extent of the impact of covid-19 pandemic on socio-economic wellbeing of Nigerians.

The Problematique

The unprecedented pandemic and the jostle to curtail its spread created major disruptions in the nation's economy and the lives of businesses in Nigeria. One major challenge was starvation because the Federal and states Government ordered a compulsory lockdown of most economic and social activities in order to mitigate the spread of the dreaded virus. In the light of that, people were restricted assessing their normal means of livelihood, which posed enormous challenge to the satisfaction of their basic needs. Furthermore, unemployment rates which have been a growing problem in Nigeria for several years intensified because several companies laid off their staff while others reduced their working hours due to covid-19 pandemic. Similarly, several challenges hampered the capacity of the educational system in Nigeria to make the needed transition from in-person to online teaching and learning as was the case in the more advanced and/or organized societies even in parts of Africa.

The international benchmark for the allocation of 15% of national budget to education sector has never been met in Nigeria; a situation which had led to frequent industrial actions in the education sector prior to the outbreak of the pandemic. In the year 2020 the federal government allocation to education was a paltry 568 billion naira and due to complications arising from the persistent nature of the corona virus, the amount was further reduced to 509 billion naira. This adversely affected the educational system-in the country, (Okwuosa & Modibbo 2021). It gave rise to the inability of schools to provide the necessary apparatus and infrastructures needed for electronic learning from home. Flowing from the identified lapses, the paper aimed to:

- 1) Ascertain the impact of covid-19 pandemic on education in Nigeria.
- 2) Investigate the impact of covid-19 pandemic on employment in Nigeria.
- 3) Find out the extent of the impact of covid-19 pandemic on the satisfaction of basic needs of Nigerians.

Conceptual Issues

Covid-19 Pandemic

SARS-CoV virus is a “Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Corona virus” which was first discovered in Guangdong province of southern China in 2002, alleged to be an animal virus from an undefined animal reservoir. Preceding studies argued that SARS-CoV and Middle East Respiratory Syndrome (MERS-CoV) infections spread from “civet cats and dromedary camels” to humans, respectively. (Udo, Abner, Inim & Akpan, 2020). In the same direction, it was conceptualized as a family of viruses seven of which can infect people, causing common cold that stem from rhinoviruses, severe respiratory syndrome and Middle East respiratory syndrome, (Katella (2020).

Socio-Economic Wellbeing

They are things that bring improvement in the quality of life of a people directly and indirectly through income and economic resources such as basic needs, good food, shelter, clean water, clothing and household utensils or focus on life expectancy and morbidity statistics. Although certain goods or services like access to health care, educational opportunities, and the ability to buy food that meets specific nutritional guidelines may be unavailable to specific socioeconomic classes based on their ability to afford them hence, their income, Jinadu (1985). In concurring with the above view, economic wellbeing could be seen as the interrelationship among capital accumulation

industrialization, government growth, urbanization, and education. It encompasses equal or unequal distribution of income within a period, (Kuper & Kuper 1996).

Brief History of Covid-19 Virus

There has been conceptual mismatch and speculations on the source of the virus since its outbreak in Wuhan province, China in 2019. It was alleged to have originated from animals such as bats that transmitted it from animal to man, (Chidume, Oko-Out & Aro 2021). Following that, Abari and Orunbon (2020) submitted that it belongs to Nidovirales, family corona viridae, sub-family ortho coronavirinae with four areas: Alpha, beta, delta and gamma corona viruses. Alpha CoVs and beta CoVs originated from bats and rodents while delta CoVs and gamma CoVs are traceable to avian species. Incidentally, beta CoVs and SARS-CoV-1 were caught from bats in 1992 with Civet cat being the intermediary host. In the same vein, MERS-CoV was separated from dromedary camels in 2003.

On that footing, corona virus infection case was first discovered in Guangdong province in 2003. Twenty-six countries were affected by SARS epidemic which accounted for 8000 confirmed cases and 9% mortality rate in Toronto, Hong Kong special administrative region of China, Chinese Taipei, Singapore and Hanoi in Viet Nam. In July 2003 SARS-CoV epidemic reappeared four times, three times from laboratory accidents in Singapore and Chinese Taipei and once in Southern China. It reappeared in December 2019 in Wuhan province of China. The first covid-19 case in Africa was recorded by Egypt on February 14th 2020. Precisely in Nigeria, the first case was recorded in Lagos on February 27th 2020, (Udo, Abner, Inim & Akpan 2020). That was heralded by the detection of covid-19 eleven days after when the contact of an Italian national on 9th March, 2020 was discovered. Subsequently, there was incessant spread of the virus across the thirty-six states of Nigeria with Lagos state considered as the epicenter of the virus. The federal government revised downwards the 2020 budget by more than ₦71 billion because corona virus affected the nations revenue. Such spiral effect spanned through every other sector in the nation, (Alagboso & Abubakar 2020).

Remarkably, the virus could be transmitted to a human being through the mouth or nose in small liquid particles such as small aerosols or larger respiratory droplets when people speak, cough, sneeze, breathe heavily and sing. When someone is in close contact of less than a meter apart from an infected patient, it could get into the persons mouth or eyes. Another form of

transmission is through handshakes and hugging with infected person. Therefore, people were cautioned to stay two meters away from anyone who is not a member of his/her immediate household, (Total Health Trust Ltd 2020). More so, respiratory droplets among people in close contact could as well lead to the virus infection. Next is through aerosol transmission like spending a long period of time with infected persons indoors, in crowded, inadequately ventilated places, offices, restaurants, night clubs and places of worships. In the same perspective, it spreads when an infected person sneezes, coughs or touches surfaces or objects like tables, doorknobs, handrails. People contract the virus when uninfected persons touch the contaminated surfaces and touch their eyes, noses or mouths without sanitizing their hands first, (World Health Organization 2020).

Theoretical Framework

The paper relied on Securitization Theory as it's framework of analysis. The theory is anchored on understanding who securitizes (securitizing actor), on what issues (threat), for when (referent object), why with what results, and not least, under what conditions. It is the elevation of an issue beyond the level of everyday politics, which justifies the use of emergency measures to deal with it. The major proponents of the theory are Copenhagen School (1980's), Jaap de Wilde, Ole Wæver (1989, 1995) with contributions and revisions from Thierry Balzacq (2005, 2011), Ralf Emmers (2007), Juha A Vuori (2008, 2001) Matt McDonald (2008), Rita Floyd (2010), Holger Stritzel (2014) among others. Securitization connotes the process of state actors changing subjects from regular political issues into affairs of security. As such, unusual means are employed in the name of security. Securitization seeks to make plain how a security issue can be changed into a threat that deserves to be overcome.

Tenets of the Theory: Securitization Theory has the following tenets:

- 1) It establishes the security character of public problems
- 2) There is a social commitment that results from a collective acceptance that a phenomenon is a threat and has to be fixed
- 3) There is a possibility of creating a particular policy.
- 4) There is usually an existence of emergency measures and
- 5) Performance of an act by speaking (illocutionary)

Application of the Theory to the Study

Securitization theory is relevant to this study because the global response to covid-19 embodies all the essential features of securitization. The unprecedented spread of corona

virus that was declared a pandemic by World Health Organization (an actor) provoked fear of insecurity as human beings felt threatened and was afraid of being infected with it. It became securitized as it threatened and changed the existing order of political, economic, social and environmental wellbeing of Nigerians despite the attempts made by the Federal and States government, World Health Organization and Nigeria Center for Disease Control to curtail the spread of the virus. There was lockdown order that restricted movement of people halted all activities and resulted to social and economic contraction of all Nigerians. Furthermore, the educational lives of people, employment situation and affordability of basic needs (food, transport, water, health, housing etc) by people were threatened. Thus, the need for pursuit of freedom from such threat became germane. The audience assessed it and provided understanding of the kind of threat which was accepted by the public. That led to preventive action being taken by the legitimate actors to curtail the threat of the virus. However, the effectiveness of the action taken depended on the state having a legal institution to mitigate the threat of covid-19 virus on the justification and agreement of the actors.

Methodology

This paper employed qualitative method both in data collection and analysis specifically, secondary sources of data were employed largely from journals, textbooks, newspapers, web pages and government documents among others. The data were analyzed through historical and interpretative methods.

Impact of Covid-19 on Socio-Economic Wellbeing of Nigerians

The educational system in Nigeria was affected because of the shutdown which led to disruption of formal academic learning. It not only revealed the poor state of infrastructure and facilities in the health sector of Nigeria but also revealed the reality of the dilapidation and poor funding of the educational sector whose effect was so severe. Whereas other nations around the world, including many in Africa, transited to virtual learning platforms, Nigeria could not adapt easily due to lack of facilities necessary to operate virtual classes, poor provision of the internet network, unstable power supply, high cost of mobile data and other challenges. The strategy of learning from home proclaimed by the Nigerian Ministry of Education which would have entailed teaching and learning *via* radio and televisions yielded little or no dividends due to epileptic supply of electricity in Nigeria and even the unavailability of those gadgets in many home. Majority of Nigerians live below poverty threshold which made them unable to afford the

needed items for such mode of education let alone owning and fuelling generators for academic purposes, (Okwuosa & Modibbo 2021). In the same vein, it created significant inequalities in the education sector. Those in private schools precisely in the urban areas engaged their students with ease through online teaching. The less privileged that are mostly in the rural and crowded urban public schools were unable to enjoy such privilege. Children in rural and urban public and low-class private schools could therefore not keep up with their peers in elite private schools because of inability to access digital tools required for e-learning thus the effect persisted, (Agbele & Oyelade 2020).

Whereas governments, private sector players and key education stakeholders synergized to promote continued learning and bridge potential learning gaps for - about 90% of their citizens in high-income countries through remote learning opportunities less than 25% of low-income countries offered any type of remote learning at all. Instead they attempted to use television and radio to reach their learners, and even that was with limited success. Just about 23% of countries in sub-Saharan Africa combined online and broadcast media platforms, (The Education Partnership Centre 2020). In the same context, about 30 million learners in Nigeria were temporarily out of school amidst covid-19. Beyond that, teacher-learner interaction or face-to-face interaction and learning was displaced which led to a significant drop in the quality of education with the disruption in academic activities, (Amorighoye 2020). The learning norm in Nigeria has been through physical contact which made the adoption of information communication technology to be at rudimentary stage. Precisely, Nigerian universities have not adequately embraced the use of information communication technology simply because of poor educational budget, lack of infrastructures required for information communication technology and lack of welfare programmes. That is largely due to the funding gap arising from government's noncompliance with the 15-20% funding benchmark stipulated by United Nations Education Scientific and Cultural Organization, (UNESCO) (Udo, Abner, Inim, & Akpan 2020).

To further elaborate, many people could not afford online education in Nigeria because about 50% of the populations live in abject poverty which made access to three square meals difficult despite the palliative measures the government claimed to have provided. Several students do not have access to radios and televisions in addition to the epileptic electricity supply in the country. Access to educational resources such as internet was a mirage on its own for many students. That widened the gap between the have and have

not, (Op- Ed contributor 2020). Similarly, public universities in the country were closed to all academic activities, both physical and online, due to ten months strike by the Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU) to protest the poor state of infrastructure in the universities and the poor working conditions of the lecturers, (Tamrat & Teferra, 2020). In addition, several lecturers in Nigeria lack the requisite competence needed for effective utilization of digital educational technologies hence educational system was negatively affected, (Ajilore, 2020).

The restrictions placed on movement due to covid-19 made several staff of informal (41.5million) micro enterprises (96% of all businesses in the country) which accounted for more than 80% of total employment, to lose their jobs either by closing down or scaling back operations, (Oludayo, 2020). In a similar vein, the contraction of Nigerian economy by 6.1% was a 5% drop from 3.2% decline previously forecasted by the World bank and the steepest in the past ten years. This was due largely to the drop in export of oil amidst covid-19 and the resultant loss of job accounted translated to 27% (over 21 million) of unemployed Nigerians, (Kazeem 2020). It was further revealed from the National Bureau of Statistics report that, in 2018 the figure of working age bracket that were unemployed was 23.1% and in 2019 which heralded covid-19 and the resultant lockdown order globally, the figure went up slightly to 24%. By the second quarter of 2020, the unemployment rate in Nigeria increased to 27.1% with about twenty-two million unemployed unable to work and earn, (Olasope 2020). In line with this trend, the increase in unemployment continued from what it was in the second quarter to 33.3% in the period between December and March 2021. That suggests that more than half of the labour force are unemployed or underemployed, (Olurounbi, 2021). Daily Trust, (2020) affirmed that, 42 percent of Nigerian workers lost their jobs and that 79 percent of households in Nigeria had diminishing incomes as a result of covid-19 restrictions.

Laying credence to that, Momoh (2020) stated that, there was a significant increase in unemployment in Nigeria due to covid-19 pandemic. As a result of economic difficulty, several companies gave up their office spaces while employees were asked to work from their homes, (Momoh, 2020). Given the rate of unemployment, pressure on consumers heightened because food prices rose more than 20% year-on-year. Prior to covid-19 pandemic, a measure of garri (local staple food) was sold for ₦500. Amidst the virus outbreak it increased to ₦2000 and caused the money and food budgeted for a week to

be consumed in three days. Other food items such as fishes, egg and meat were scarce to purchase which made Nigerians hungry and unable to maintain a good livelihood. In a similar vein, eating three square meals was difficult. The depletion of blood glucose in the body caused by the stomach being empty longer than necessary when the human brain is supposed to be at 80/120mg/dl for efficient performance could be harmful to Nigerians. Remarkably, more than 37% of households were exposed to hike in prices of major food items, while about 12% of them experienced reduction in food consumption in order to manage the impact of the shocks. Following that, Nigerians changed their priority by buying affordable food stuffs while skipping the consumption of foods and fruits considered as luxury (Nwobi, 2020).

Amidst that, peril stared workers on their faces as fishes, egg and meat were scarce to purchase for children feeding. Workers were hungry and could not eke out their livelihoods. Thus, they had to beg and did other undignified things to survive. Most households drank garri and salt with mostly untreated water because they could not afford to buy the regular treated water packaged in sachets, (Nwobi 2020). Hence, Nwobi, Enibe, Ugwunnadi & Husaini (2019) concurred that, eating of three-square meals became a mirage for many Nigerians. He noted that, when a stomach is empty longer than necessary, glucose and protein contents in the body drops, and that, the depletion of blood glucose in the body when the human brain is supposed to be at 80/120mg/dl for efficient performance could be harmful to workers. Remarkably, more than 37% of households were exposed to increase in prices of major food items, while about 12% of them experienced reduction in food consumption in order to manage the impact of the shocks, (Olurounbi, 2020). Following that, Nigerians reconsidered their priority by getting food stuffs they could afford and skipped consumption of fruits and some foods adjudged as luxury. The mitigation plan was to ration the quantity and quality of food consumed in order to survive, (Obadofin, 2020). The following table shows the prices of some food items before and during the lockdown.

Table 1: Average Prices of Some Food Items in the Market Pre and During Covid-19 Pandemic in Nigeria (Prices in Naira “₦”).

Food Items.	Unit of Sales.	Pre Covid-19.	During Covid-19.
Rice	50kg bag	8,500, 14,500	30,000-35,000
Rice	(1 Paint bucket)	2500	3000
Rice	(1 Cup)	100-120	150
Yam	Regular (Small)	150	250-500

Yam	Regular (medium)	700	500-900 1000
Yam	Regular (Large)	900-1000	1,600
Beans	100kg bag	25,000	65,000
Beans	(1Paint rubber	350	2400-2500
Beans	(1 Cup)	40	120-130
Garri	(80KG)	6000	18,000-18,500
Garri	1 Paint bucket	400	1000-1300
Garri	1Cup	25-30	70
Green Leaf Vegetable	Small Bundle 0.16KG	50	50
Tomatoes	40kg	-	8,000-22,000
Tomatoes	25kg	-	9,500
Tomatoes	Small basket)	700	1000
Onions	100 KG	-	10,000-29,000
Onions	1kg	150	250-500
Fish	0.85KG	-	-
Meat (Beef)	(5-6 small pieces)	300	500-1000
Meat (Beef)	A pan weight	800	1,500
Crayfish	A Heap 0.01KG	50	100
Chicken	Broiler	1600	2500-3000
Chicken	Old layer	1200	1800-2000
Palm Oil	25- liter keg	7500-8000	10,000-12,000
Palm Oil	1 Bottle	300	450
Sachet Water	1 Bag(20pcs)	100	200
Sachet Water	1 sachet	5	20

Source: Author (2021).

From the above table, most items experienced astronomical increase in prices. Price of item like green leaves or vegetable did not change but there was reduction in in the quantity sold. To underscore the accuracy of the above findings, Gourlay, Amankwah and Zezza (2021) held that many households that enjoyed food security before the pandemic became food insecure with effect from the month of July 2020 and beyond as a result of disruption caused by the ravaging corona virus.

In another dimension, the purchasing power of people decreased drastically as a result of lack of money in circulation. It became intensified with the increases in the price of goods. Most importantly is that, the prices of essential products such as water and food items doubled in price given the panic buying and hoarding as supplies could not meet the demand of goods and services. There was increase in cost of transportation because public vehicle drivers were mandated to reduce the number of passengers they conveyed at a time in line with covid-19 protocol. On the basis of that, commercial drivers plying the roads decided to increase the transport fare in order to make up the shortfall arising from reduced number of passengers conveyed at a time. Entrepreneurs who survive on daily sales were unable to meet their family daily needs, (Olatokewa, 2020).

Empirically, Kazeem, (2020) submits that, Seun Adebajo's family introduced food bank in up market Lagos suburb with the motive of feeding 300 people from nearby neighborhood with lower income as a result of covid-19 lockdown. Subsequently, the food bank registered an increase to feeding of about 3000 people on a daily basis. These people had to struggle without income which was a mark of the impact of the pandemic especially on the vulnerable and lower-income households in Lagos (Kazeem, 2020).

Stretching the point further on that, United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (2020) observed that, the various control measures are the same everywhere such that; the situation was applicable to all. About 75.77% of the people lacked food, 52.46% were restricted from accessing basic needs and, 12.51% from decent shelter. The inability of most households to buy goods and services led to maltreatment by their spouses. Given economic crisis, 43.34% had reduced income. It was more pronounced among the vulnerable where 27.72% suffered restriction to income sources, 16.30% suffered loss of income and damage to their capacity to earn a living, (United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees, 2020).

Concluding Remarks

From the foregoing presentation, it could be seen that, the rapid spread of the covid-19 virus in Nigeria from March 2020 constituted enormous challenges to socio-economic activities as its containment strategies interfered with individuals' daily lives and led to severe economic loss and social disruption in employment, basic needs and the educational system of Nigeria. For instance, despite the directive of the Ministry of Education for migration to online teaching and learning, educational activities were seriously disrupted due to lack of the requisite infrastructure to give effect to the directive. Findings from the study revealed that, there was lack of facilities, poor internet network and unstable power supply necessary to operate virtual classes. There was also loss of employment because organizations had to either close or scale back operations and meeting of lives basic needs was difficult which made even daily feeding very difficult for most families contrary to what obtained before the outbreak of the pandemic and implementation of its control measures. All these posed serious threat to socio-economic wellbeing of Nigerians during the lockdown and beyond.

Recommendations

Arising from the findings, the paper recommends as follows:

- 1) To ensure further mitigation of the impact of covid-19 on education, the government should provide solar powered educational devices, preloaded with off-line academic resources especially to the vulnerable communities and disadvantaged students.
- 2) The cost of capacity building training should be subsidized by the government. If the financial barrier is removed, there will be a significant increase on the number of people going for capacity building in order to scale down on unemployment rate.
- 3) To address unemployment, school curriculum should be re-designed in line with our current needs to include digital literacy, creativity among others.
- 4) Engaging in sustainable agriculture. The federal government should make grants available for willing Nigerians to get involved in agriculture. This will not only improve basic needs but would also create employment for the teeming youths.

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